

Farmed fish welfare-suffering assessment and impact on product quality

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Abstract

Fish welfare, suffering and the perception of pain were debated, together with several factors reducing *infra vitam* welfare of farmed fish (genetic, environment, density, malnutrition, starvation, cataracts, deformities, vaccination side effects, transport, handling, confinement, crowding, harvesting, killing method). Behavioural and physiological stress responses were considered as indicators of welfare reduction. The effects of pre-slaughter management practices, and the most commonly used stunning/slaughtering methods on welfare and quality reduction of farmed fish were discussed. A number of indicators can be used to assess fish welfare-suffering, both in a scientific and practical context, such as behavioural, haematic, cellular, tissue *post mortem* fish stress and quality indicators, but none of them are optimal. The best strategy for a reliable assessment of fish welfare/suffering and their impact on product quality is a multidisciplinary approach that takes into account animal behaviour and the different biochemical and physiological *ante mortem* and *post mortem* processes involved: several components, all influenced in a similar way by the same condition, suggest real welfare and quality reduction.